

A framework for chemical hazard assessments under ‘Safe and Sustainable by Design’ using multiple in silico tools

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Editor's Note: This article is part of the special series “Getting New Approach Methods (NAMs) into Environmental Assessment, Management, and Practice.” The series presents a collection of articles on how NAMs are being developed to meet adopter needs, inform regulation, policy, and/or decision making, as well as their application in environment risk (and/or impact) assessment and management.

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4 **Key words:** Safe and Sustainable by Design; in silico tools; (Q)SARs; hazard
5 assessment; uncertainty

6

7 Abstract

8 The hazard identification of chemicals is a key step of the 'Safe and Sustainable by
9 Design' (SSbD) framework introduced by the European Commission, aiming to eliminate
10 hazardous substances early in innovation. In this context, *in silico* methods such as
11 (Quantitative) Structure-Activity Relationship ((Q)SAR) models offer rapid, cost-effective,
12 and animal-free alternatives for early-stage hazard screening. The Partnership for the
13 Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) is developing a toolbox to facilitate SSbD
14 assessments containing numerous (Q)SAR models. Challenges, however, exist in using
15 and combining multiple *in silico* tools. Here, we developed a workflow to assess chemical
16 hazards using multiple *in silico* tools within the PARC toolbox. The workflow consists of
17 three phases: 1) the preparation stage, 2) running the models, and 3) the evaluation stage.
18 To demonstrate the approach, we applied it to a case study comparing Bisphenol A,
19 Isosorbide, and Bisphenol AP. Tools from the PARC toolbox were screened for relevance,
20 transparency, and open access availability. Only models aligned with SSbD required
21 endpoints and adequately documented via (Q)SAR Model Reporting Formats were
22 retained. The properties assessed in this study cover carcinogenicity, germ cell
23 mutagenicity, reproductive toxicity, endocrine disruption, persistence, bioaccumulation,
24 and aquatic toxicity. Predictions were filtered using applicability domain criteria and
25 reliability scores. Next, three strategies were applied for integrating different model
26 outputs. Model agreement varied across endpoints and integration methods. This
27 emphasizes the possibility of different SSbD assessment outcomes and thus the need for
28 transparent documentation of the chosen strategy and explicit handling of uncertainty.
29 Our study demonstrates how multiple models can systematically and transparently be
30 integrated via the developed workflow. Key areas for improvement are to refine
31 integration strategies, harmonize the definition and communication of applicability
32 domains across tools, expand *in silico* coverage for currently underrepresented endpoints,
33 and to develop approaches to consider data gaps in SSbD assessments.

34

35 Introduction

36 The increasing number and volume of chemicals and materials released into the
37 environment are a growing concern for both human health and the environment (Almroth
38 et al., 2022; UNEP, 2019). To better address this issue, the 'Chemicals Strategy for
39 Sustainability' has been published in Europe (European Commission, 2020). A key
40 component of this strategy is the concept of Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD),
41 which promotes the integration of safety and sustainability considerations as early as
42 possible in the innovation process and throughout the entire product lifecycle.

43 SSbD is intended to guide the development of chemicals and materials through iterative
44 design and assessment cycles. In this framework, potential hazards should be identified
45 at early stages of development so that problematic substances can be avoided or
46 replaced before large investments are made in production or commercialization (Caldeira
47 et al., 2022; Garmendia Aguirre et al., 2025). While minimizing intrinsic hazards is a
48 central element of SSbD, effective chemicals management also relies on risk-based
49 decision-making that considers both hazard and exposure. Hazard identification,
50 therefore, represents an early screening step within a broader decision-making
51 framework that ultimately integrates exposure assessment and risk characterization.

52 Within the SSbD framework, hazard assessment focuses particularly on properties that
53 are considered critical under European chemical regulations, such as the Classification,
54 Labelling and Packaging (CLP) and the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and
55 Restriction of Chemicals (REACH). The 'most hazardous substances' -which include
56 substances that are carcinogenic, mutagenic and/or reprotoxic (CMR), persistent,
57 bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT), and endocrine disrupting (ED)- should be filtered out
58 early in the process as their use cannot be considered as 'safe and sustainable'.

59 Traditionally, hazard assessments and further risk assessments required under CLP and
60 REACH involve collecting experimental data (ECHA, 2011). At early stages of innovation,
61 however, experimental data are often scarce because new substances have not yet
62 undergone extensive testing. Under such conditions, predictive approaches are required
63 to identify potential hazards and guide early design decisions. In silico methods, including

64 (Quantitative) Structure–Activity Relationship ((Q)SAR) models, provide a promising
65 solution for this purpose. (Q)SAR models predict chemical properties and biological
66 effects based on molecular structure. Although these models remain underused in current
67 risk assessments (Thomas et al., 2019), (Q)SAR models are particularly well-suited to
68 identify areas of potential concern in the early innovation stages targeted by SSbD, since
69 they are rapid, cost-effective, and do not require animal testing (Garmendia Aguirre et al.,
70 2025).

71 Despite their advantages, the use of (Q)SAR models raises several methodological
72 challenges. First, individual models often have limited applicability domains, meaning that
73 predictions may only be reliable for certain types of chemicals. Second, multiple models
74 may exist for the same hazard endpoint (e.g., an overview [here](#)), which can result in
75 conflicting predictions. Third, authorities are often promoting the use of integrated in silico
76 models since this increases the confidence of the results (EMA, 2023), while integrating
77 results from different models into a coherent interpretation requires transparent decision
78 rules and careful consideration of uncertainty. Existing studies and guidance documents,
79 such as general guidance on using in silico models (Benfenati et al., 2019), the studies
80 and guidance on weight-of-evidence (WoE) approaches (Caldeira et al., 2023; EFSA
81 Scientific Committee et al., 2017; Leder et al., 2015; Lorenz et al., 2021; van Dijk et al.,
82 2022), and the OECD (Q)SAR Assessment Framework (QAF) (OECD, 2023a, 2024),
83 provide principles for evaluating and combining lines of evidence. However, practical
84 workflows for applying multiple in silico tools within the SSbD context remain limited.
85 Furthermore, interpreting predictions from multiple models requires expert judgement.
86 Agreement between models does not necessarily guarantee that predictions are reliable,
87 and experienced toxicologists and environmental scientists must evaluate model outputs
88 in the context of modelling information (e.g., chemical structure, applicability domain (AD)
89 of the models, and prediction uncertainties), biological mechanisms, and regulatory
90 endpoints (Sarigiannis et al., 2023).

91 In this study, we therefore develop a workflow for conducting hazard assessments using
92 multiple in silico tools in the context of SSbD. The workflow is designed to support
93 transparent model selection, reliability evaluation, and integration of predictions. To

94 illustrate its application, the workflow is applied to a case study involving Bisphenol A
95 (BPA), Bisphenol AP (BPAP), and Isosorbide, representing a substitution scenario
96 relevant to SSbD assessments. The aims of this study are therefore to:

- 97 1. Develop a structured workflow for applying multiple in silico hazard prediction tools
98 identified under the Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
99 (PARC) (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023) within the SSbD context and included in the
100 PARC SSbD toolbox (Sarigiannis et al., 2024);
- 101 2. Demonstrate the workflow through a case study involving BPA and two potential
102 alternative substances;
- 103 3. Explore strategies for evaluating, integrating, and communicating model outputs
104 while explicitly addressing uncertainty based on previously published literature and
105 the QAF (Benfenati et al., 2019; EFSA Scientific Committee et al., 2017).

106 The study focuses specifically on (Q)SAR-based approaches, including both traditional
107 descriptor-based models and machine learning–driven models, as these represent
108 some of the most mature and widely accepted in silico methods for hazard prediction.
109 While (Q)SAR predictions cannot replace experimental data or expert evaluation, they
110 can play a central role in early-stage screening and prioritization within SSbD
111 assessments.

112 Methods

113 Framework design

114 To support the use of multiple in silico models in SSbD hazard assessments, a structured
115 workflow was developed in this study. The workflow was based on the QAF and published
116 documents outlining how uncertainty in (Q)SAR predictions can be considered and how
117 their results can be integrated (Benfenati et al., 2019; EFSA Scientific Committee et al.,
118 2017; OECD, 2024).

119 The workflow aims to guide users through the selection, evaluation, and integration of
120 predictions from multiple in silico tools in a transparent and reproducible manner. The
121 workflow consists of three phases:

- 122 • Preparation stage, in which the assessment context (e.g., target chemicals) is
123 defined, relevant hazard endpoints are identified, and suitable in silico models
124 are selected;
- 125 • Model execution stage, in which the selected models are run, and prediction
126 outputs are collected;
- 127 • Evaluation stage, in which the reliability of model predictions is assessed, and
128 results from different models are integrated.

129 An overview of the workflow developed and applied in this study is presented in Figure 1.

130 Problem formulation

131 The present study demonstrates the workflow based on a case study conducted within
132 the PARC project, for which the chemical Bisphenol A (BPA, CAS: 80-05-7) and two
133 potential alternative substances, Bisphenol AP (BPAP, CAS: 1571-75-1) and Isosorbide
134 (CAS: 652-67-5) were selected to test a range of tools for SSbD assessments (PARC et
135 al., 2024).

136 The selected substances represent a typical substitution scenario in which a well-known
137 substance with recognized hazard concerns (BPA) is compared with potential alternative
138 substances. BPA is widely studied and has known regulatory concerns, while BPAP and
139 Isosorbide represent structurally different alternatives. This combination allows the
140 workflow to be tested across substances with different chemical structures and different
141 levels of available background knowledge.

142 The hazard assessment focused on endpoints relevant to identifying substances of
143 concern under the SSbD framework. These include properties associated with CMR
144 effects, properties determining the environmental fate and behaviour for PBT
145 classification, as well as ED-related properties. CMR and PBT properties are used to
146 identify substances of very high concern and must be assessed under the SSbD

147 framework to prevent the use of the most hazardous substances (Caldeira et al., 2022;
148 Garmendia Aguirre et al., 2025), and ED are the recent-included endpoints in the CLP
149 regulation.

150 Selection of relevant (Q)SAR models

151 A wide range of in silico tools are available to predict chemical hazards, and different
152 platforms may provide models for different endpoints. Within the PARC project, an
153 inventory of tools relevant for SSbD hazard assessments was previously compiled
154 (Sarigiannis et al., 2023). From this inventory, models were selected based on three
155 criteria:

- 156 • relevance to hazard endpoints required in SSbD assessments,
- 157 • availability through open-access platforms,
- 158 • adequate documentation through (Q)SAR Model Reporting Formats (QMRF).

159 An overview of the platforms used in this study is presented in Table 1. These include
160 VEGA (Benfenati et al., 2013), JANUS , EPI Suite (US EPA, 2012), the Danish (Q)SAR
161 Database (DTU, n.d.), the Mistra SafeChem in-silico toolbox (not openly available at time
162 of publication), and the OECD QSAR Toolbox (OECD, 2023b). Not all platforms provide
163 models for all hazard endpoints. Therefore, multiple platforms were used to ensure
164 sufficient coverage across the endpoints considered in the assessment. QMRFs were
165 analyzed to filter out models that were developed for endpoints that are irrelevant for the
166 SSbD assessment (such as anaerobic degradation) and avoid double-inclusion (for
167 example, some models are included in both the Danish (Q)SAR database and OECD
168 QSAR Toolbox). An overview of the different platforms used, and endpoints predicted, is
169 presented in Table 1, and a list of all the individual models used in this work, and the
170 reasoning why to include or exclude them, is presented in the supplementary information
171 (SI). In some cases, platforms provide consensus models that integrate predictions from
172 several individual models. In such cases, we used the outputs of the consensus model
173 rather than those of the individual models to avoid double-counting predictions.

174 Running the models and collecting predictions

175 For each substance, predictions were generated using the selected models across all
176 relevant hazard endpoints. The types of outputs produced by the models vary depending
177 on the endpoint and modelling approach. Some models provide quantitative predictions
178 (e.g., toxicity values), while others produce categorical outputs (e.g., positive or negative
179 predictions for a specific hazard class). Detailed information for each model can be found
180 in the SI.

181 Predictions from different models were first grouped according to the hazard endpoint
182 they addressed. This grouping allowed predictions from multiple models to be evaluated
183 collectively within each endpoint before integration across endpoints.

184 Evaluation of prediction reliability

185 After generating model predictions, the reliability of the predictions was evaluated.
186 However, the prediction reliability information provided by different platforms varies. Most
187 platforms (Except for EPI Suite) provide information regarding the QMRF and the way to
188 evaluate the AD that can be used to evaluate prediction reliability. Some platforms provide
189 additional measurements besides AD for reliability (an overview see the SI material). In
190 this study, two evaluation approaches were considered.

191 In the simple assessment approach, predictions were retained only if they fell within the
192 AD of the model. Predictions outside the applicability domain were excluded from further
193 analysis. Depending on the platform, applicability domain information may be provided
194 either as a binary indicator (in-domain or out-of-domain) or as a continuous reliability
195 score. In the case of binary output, only the in-domain predictions were considered. In the
196 case where the AD is assessed as a continuous value, only predictions with high reliability
197 (>80%) are considered. For EPI Suite, basic recommendations provided by the platform
198 (e.g., the molecular weight range) were used as a proxy of AD.

199 In the advanced assessment approach, additional expert evaluation was applied to
200 examine predictions that fell outside the formal applicability domain. In such cases,
201 additional information was considered, including structural similarity to compounds in the
202 model training set, presence of mechanistic alerts, and supporting evidence from related

203 models. This step allows experienced assessors to evaluate whether certain predictions
204 may still be informative despite formal applicability domain limitations.

205 Integration of predictions

206 When multiple models are available for the same endpoint, different strategies can be
207 used to integrate predictions into a single outcome. In this study, three integration
208 strategies were evaluated based on approaches previously described in the literature
209 (Benfenati et al., 2019):

- 210 • Majority vote, in which the most frequently occurring prediction among the models
211 is selected;
- 212 • Mean approach, applied when quantitative predictions are available;
- 213 • Conservative approach, in which the most hazardous prediction is selected as a
214 precautionary estimate.

215 These integration strategies represent different ways of addressing uncertainty and
216 weighing evidence from multiple models. The choice of integration strategy can influence
217 the final outcome of the hazard assessment and should therefore be transparently
218 documented. In practice, the selection of the most appropriate integration approach
219 requires expert judgement and may depend on the assessment context.

220 Results

221 Overview of the workflow application

222 The developed workflow was applied to three case study chemicals: Bisphenol A (BPA),
223 Bisphenol AP (BPAP), and Isosorbide. These substances were evaluated across hazard
224 endpoints relevant to the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework, including
225 carcinogenicity, germ cell mutagenicity, reproductive toxicity, endocrine disruption,
226 persistence, bioaccumulation, and aquatic toxicity.

227 Across these endpoints, predictions were generated using multiple (Q)SAR models
228 available across different in silico platforms. The outputs of these models included both
229 quantitative predictions (e.g., predicted toxicity values) and categorical outputs (e.g.,

230 positive or negative predictions for a hazard class). For each endpoint, predictions from
231 different models were grouped before evaluating their reliability and integrating their
232 results.

233 Model availability from studied platforms

234 Persistence

235 For persistence, the half-life in different environmental compartments and ready
236 biodegradability were predicted. These are the required endpoints under European
237 legislation. VEGA (www.vegahub.eu) offers both a classification model and a quantitative
238 model that provides a continuous value for the three compartments: water, sediment, and
239 soil. These two models should be used in conjunction to ensure consistency and avoid
240 conflicts. The models are integrated within the JANUS software, which refers to REACH
241 requirements and thresholds. An example of how to apply and interpret these models has
242 been published (Benfenati et al., 2025). Other platforms used for persistence predictions
243 are EPI Suite and the Danish (Q)SAR platform, both of which have combination methods
244 for the prediction of ready biodegradability, and the Mistra SafeChem *in silico* Toolbox
245 v1.1, which contains two classification models for persistence in soil and two classification
246 models for ready biodegradability.

247 Bioaccumulation

248 For bioaccumulation, the bioconcentration factor (BCF) and LogKow were considered.
249 VEGA has four BCF models. Two of them, Meylan and Arnot-Gobas, are
250 reimplementations of those available within the EPI Suite platform. VEGA automatically
251 provides the evaluation of the AD to be used for the prediction, while this is not possible
252 with EPI Suite. For these two added reasons, the BCF models from EPI Suite were not
253 used in this exercise. The Mistra SafeChem *in silico* Toolbox has two classification
254 models for BCF in fish. As logKow plays a crucial role in the BCF models, it's important
255 to understand the impact of this parameter. A detailed explanation of the consequences
256 of the logKow on the BCF models is reported (Benfenati et al., 2025).

257 Carcinogenicity

258 To predict carcinogenic properties under the SSbD framework, all available models from
259 the Danish (Q)SAR database, VEGA, and Mistra SafeChem were taken into account. As
260 the individual models can be based on different types of studies (i.e., animal vs. human
261 data, data on different animal species and different genders), different results might be
262 generated in these models for the same chemical structure. It is thus recommended to
263 consider these indications within each platform, since the developers may have optimized
264 the way to integrate the results. Therefore, for VEGA, the JANUS Carcinogenicity
265 CONSENSUS model was run, and for the Danish (Q)SAR Database, the strategy to
266 assign a positive or non-positive overall call was applied (DTU Food, 2018). The strategy
267 to integrate the results across platforms was equal to the one applied by EFSA to prioritize
268 which botanicals found in vegetables available on the European market should require
269 further studies in order to clarify issues related to their health effects (EFSA, 2025).

270 Germ Cell Mutagenicity

271 The CLP hazard class germ cell mutagenicity is primarily concerned with substances that
272 may cause mutations in germ cells of humans that can be transmitted to the progeny.
273 However, the results from mutagenicity or genotoxicity tests *in vitro* and in mammalian
274 somatic and germ cells *in vivo* are also considered in the classification. Assessing the
275 mutagenicity of a substance requires the coverage of several key endpoints, specifically
276 gene mutation and chromosomal damage, including both clastogenic and aneugenic
277 effects. Germ cell mutagenicity is generally evaluated *in vivo* by heritable germ cell
278 mutagenicity tests, such as the rodent dominant lethal mutation test or mouse heritable
279 translocation assay. For detecting gene mutations, the Ames test is widely used, which
280 detects mutations in bacterial strains. On the other hand, the *in vitro* or *in vivo*
281 micronucleus test, and the *in vitro* or *in vivo* chromosomal aberration assay, are used to
282 evaluate structural and numerical chromosomal changes. Together, these
283 complementary approaches provide a thorough understanding of a substance's potential
284 to cause gene mutations and chromosomal damage. In general, evidence of germ cell
285 toxicity in humans or mammals is required for classification in category 1 of CLP, unless
286 there is supporting evidence that somatic cell mutagenicity or genotoxicity is also

287 applicable in germ cells. Somatic cell genotoxicity tests *in vivo*, supported by *in vitro* tests
288 or structure-activity relationships to known germ cell mutagens, warrant classification to
289 category 2. It is important to note that although evidence of a single mechanism of germ
290 or somatic cell mutagenicity and/or genotoxicity is sufficient for classification, a negative
291 result in any individual test does not indicate a substance is safe.

292 For these endpoints, a large battery of models is present on different platforms. VEGA
293 has several models for Ames, providing also a consensus tool. Moreover, VEGA and the
294 Danish (Q)SAR Database have a list of models related to the *in vitro* and *in vivo*
295 micronucleus test. Different strategies can be used for the application of these models,
296 depending on the regulatory context. For SSbD purposes, all available models were used
297 to predict mutagenic properties.

298 Reproductive toxicity & endocrine disruption

299 In the case of reproductive toxicity, the models could be divided into two main groups:
300 models specific for reproductive toxicity, which are primarily based on human and animal
301 data, and models for ED. The ED models are included here as there is a significant
302 overlap between reprotoxicity and ED-related endpoints. The ED models relate to
303 reproductive toxicity by varying degrees, making it difficult to draw the line between
304 models belonging to both groups and strictly ED models. Making such a differentiation
305 between reprotoxicity and ED may leave out potentially useful information. The ED
306 models include one general model based on human and wildlife data (VEGA) as well as
307 many mechanistic *in vitro* models linked to reproduction to varying degrees, some directly
308 and some indirectly. These mechanistic models can be used as supporting information
309 and indicators of research needs. However, a positive outcome in these models alone
310 should not override the results from models that are based on *in vivo* data, as their results
311 are rarely quantitative and usually cover only a single key event. For classification
312 purposes, it is currently necessary to show that effects are observed *in vivo* or in humans.
313 In addition, the mechanistic models for ED reviewed in this case study are based on *in*
314 *vitro* data that are subject to high variation due to differences in experimental conditions,
315 resulting in variable biological relevance.

316 Aquatic toxicity

317 Aquatic toxicity refers to the potential of a chemical substance to cause harmful effects
318 on aquatic organisms, such as fish, invertebrates, and algae. Under the REACH
319 Regulation, aquatic toxicity is a key environmental hazard endpoint used to assess the
320 intrinsic properties of substances and to inform risk management measures. For aquatic
321 toxicity, we applied the battery of models implemented in the VEGA software. VEGA
322 indeed contains fifteen models for acute aquatic toxicity and three for chronic aquatic
323 toxicity, covering the three trophic levels (fish, daphnia, algae). Other available models
324 from the EPI Suite platform and the Danish (Q)SAR Database were used, too. Also, for
325 aquatic toxicity, a detailed explanation on how to integrate the different models and apply
326 a WoE approach is provided. (Benfenati et al., 2025).

327 Evaluation of prediction reliability

328 Figure 2 illustrates the proportion of model predictions retained as reliable under the two
329 evaluation approaches (the simple evaluation and advanced evaluation) for the three
330 case chemicals. As expected, the advanced evaluation resulted in a larger number of
331 predictions being considered reliable compared to the simple evaluation approach.

332 Integration of predictions

333 Table 2 summarizes the combined results for each hazard property across the three
334 chemicals based on predictions retained after reliability evaluation. In general, BPA and
335 BPAP showed potential hazard signals for several endpoints, whereas Isosorbide was
336 predicted to have fewer hazard concerns.

337 The general outcome per property is the same for the simple and advanced assessment,
338 however, the prediction of the individual endpoints can be different. The full list of
339 predicted endpoints for every substance and model, as well as the combined output
340 according to the three strategies can be found in the SI. For C, M and R properties, all
341 included models covered a different endpoint. Therefore, no summary of the results was
342 created according to the three predefined strategies. Importance should be given to the
343 type of endpoint flagged and by what model. These findings illustrate that integrating
344 multiple in silico predictions can lead to different possible hazard assessment outcomes,

345 and how this should inform chemical/material innovation under the SSbD Framework is
346 user-dependent. However, the transparent documentation of integration strategies and
347 decision rules is important in the SSbD assessment.

348 Discussion

349 Selection of relevant models

350 The workflow for integrating the results for a certain property may vary depending on the
351 specific case. Once the assessment context is defined, this should be used to identify the
352 necessary endpoints. Here, the assessment context refers to the regulatory or decision-
353 making purpose of the evaluation, including the type of hazard endpoint required, the
354 stage of innovation, and the intended use of the assessment results. We have seen that
355 multiple models may be available to address the same property or endpoint, and this is
356 an advantage. For instance, in the CLP classification, mutagenicity classification requires
357 to assess permanent changes in the amount or structure of genetic material in human
358 germ cells. This definition implies covering germ cell mutations, while other regulations
359 only require mutagenicity to detect mutations in somatic cells. Further differences exist
360 not only for the regulations but also at the international level, and thus, there are different
361 procedures to evaluate a certain property depending on the geographical area.
362 Furthermore, different toxicity classes and threshold values exist in different countries.
363 This process should then be applied to the specific substance(s). The suitability of a
364 certain model indeed depends on the specific substance. We have discussed the
365 relevance of the AD to identify which prediction is reliable. Thus, it is not possible to
366 identify a model that is always reliable and another one that fails. The results are
367 substance-dependent. The user should refer to the QAF for proper guidance (OECD,
368 2024).

369 Regardless of the implications in different regulations and possible use of tools outside
370 the SSbD assessment framework (Clift et al., 2013; Nohmi, 2018), the importance of the
371 SSbD toolbox to allow users to select the most relevant properties for their specific case
372 should be emphasised, rather than being limited to a single predefined workflow with a

373 fixed set of (Q)SAR models. Flexibility in model and endpoint selection is critical to ensure
374 relevance and applicability across a wide range of substances and regulatory contexts.

375 In addition, it must be acknowledged that not all endpoints can currently be addressed
376 using *in silico* tools alone. This highlights the need for further research and development
377 to expand the applicability domain and predictive power of existing models.

378 Uncertainty of *in silico* predictions

379 Each model prediction comes with a degree of uncertainty. To address this, it is
380 recommended to use multiple models whenever possible. For example, consensus
381 models can be seen as more reliable than individual models, so that in theory we can
382 place more weight on these outcomes. However, the relative importance of outcomes is
383 something that cannot be pre-determined and needs to be defined at the start of every
384 SSbD assessment. Also, agreement between multiple models does not necessarily
385 guarantee that a prediction is correct, particularly if models rely on similar training data or
386 modelling assumptions. Therefore, interpretation of model outputs should involve expert
387 judgement from toxicologists or environmental scientists familiar with the endpoint and
388 modelling approaches.

389 The approach of combining different models can help reduce the uncertainty of
390 predictions by increasing confidence in the result. However, during this work, we
391 observed that improvements could be made in how different platforms communicate
392 information, particularly regarding predictions that fall outside the AD. Different tools
393 convey whether a prediction falls in- or outside the AD in various ways. For instance, in
394 EPI Suite, evaluating the AD is a manual process, requiring a time-consuming analysis
395 of chemical moieties and their occurrence in the substance. In contrast, tools like VEGA
396 and the Danish (Q)SAR Database automatically check several conditions to assess the
397 AD. Moreover, it is highly beneficial if a tool provides information on why a prediction falls
398 outside the AD. This allows for a manual assessment based on multiple lines of evidence,
399 enabling users to include or exclude certain values by considering similar substances in
400 the dataset and theoretical factors.

401 Within the perspective of using the results of *in silico* models for SSbD, the information
402 about the uncertainty of the prediction should be incorporated within the process. Within
403 this approach, it may be convenient to apply an evaluation of the compared hazard impact
404 associated to the candidate substituent, compared to the substance to be replaced. In
405 this scenario, the evaluation may not be an absolute one but rather a relative comparison.
406 In other words, the *in silico* models should be applied both to the target and candidate
407 substances. The information about the hazard of the target substance (which quite likely
408 is available), to be replaced, should be used to verify the correctness of the results of the
409 *in silico* models. If the candidate substance is not very different from the target, a
410 comparison of the correctness of the results can be made.

411 The granularity of the models for the same property

412 Several hazard properties need to be assessed, depending on the regulation and the
413 purpose. As stated above, it is frequent that for the same property, several endpoints exist,
414 which can differ according to defined guidelines. There is a general need to adopt a
415 standardized ontology and refer to common definitions, such as is being developed at the
416 OECD level with the Global Harmonized System (GHS) perspective. In Europe, the
417 initiative called ‘One Substance-One Assessment’ is addressing this need, too.

418 However, as observed by our analysis of the QRMFs, the development of several *in silico*
419 models started with collections of data, which do not always adhere to a single protocol.
420 Thus, there may be a misalignment between some *in silico* models and the official
421 endpoint definitions. For instance, there are models for fish acute toxicity, which use data
422 related to multiple fish species as a training set. The result of this model may refer to a
423 “generic”, not defined fish, while in other contexts, the identification of the fish species is
424 requested. Similarly, it is usual and requested in certain regulatory frameworks to provide
425 data on the Ames test generated using five different strains, with and without metabolic
426 activation. However, for the Ames test *in silico* models, the common situation is that they
427 provide a single outcome, since they are developed to merge results obtained within
428 different conditions.

429 Even more complex is the case of the models for carcinogenicity. In this case, there is a
430 range of models. Some models may relate to a single animal species, while others may
431 relate to studies conducted with different animal species and different sexes. In several
432 cases, assessments of substances are done by human experts who may consider
433 epidemiological studies and *in vitro* tests, too. Thus, these models rely on different data,
434 which in general can be called carcinogenicity, but in practice, look at different situations.

435 The case of the models for developmental toxicity and reprotoxicity is also challenging.
436 In practice, the different models cannot be compared since they refer to different
437 endpoints that cover developmental toxicity and impaired fertility. For classification
438 purposes, it is necessary to demonstrate that the adverse effect is realized in humans or
439 in experimental animals. Notably, these effects may manifest not only in the exposed
440 individual but also in subsequent generations. As a result, there are many possible
441 experimental methods that can be applied to identify reprotoxic effects, many of which
442 are time-consuming and costly. Consequently, there are relatively few models based on
443 animal/human data that are specific to this endpoint. This is something that the SSbD
444 evaluator needs to be aware of, as in the end, this would result in a data gap. How data
445 gaps can be addressed and taken into account in the evaluation approach of the SSbD
446 assessment was not part of this work but should be addressed in the future.

447 Combining results

448 Based on the strategy to combine different predictions (i.e., mean, majority, or
449 conservative approach), the final outcome may vary, meaning there are multiple SSbD
450 outcomes possible for the same use case. For example, based on the BCF predictions,
451 BPAP can potentially be non-bioaccumulative or bioaccumulative, depending on the
452 strategy applied. This illustrates that integration strategies should be explicitly defined and
453 transparently reported when using multiple *in silico* predictions. It is important to highlight
454 that there is no single best way to combine the results, and the procedure also depends
455 on practical considerations, such as time and tools available, and the preference of the
456 assessor for choosing either the most conservative value or to adopt a more weight of
457 evidence approach. In practice, expert judgement is required to determine which
458 integration strategy is most appropriate for the specific assessment context. In all cases,

459 the procedure that is taken should be declared to increase transparency and to avoid
460 bias.

461 When multiple models provide conflicting values, this is an indication of difficulties in the
462 prediction, representing in a clear way the uncertainty of the assessment. When a single
463 value is available, the evaluation becomes more difficult, and other lines of evidence
464 should be considered, such as the presence of similar substances confirming the
465 prediction (read-across approach, thus evidence-based) or the presence of a plausible
466 mechanism confirming the assessment (theoretical supporting information). Furthermore,
467 by considering additional models under the advanced assessment method, some
468 unequivocal results under the majority and mean approaches can be resolved,
469 emphasising the added value of this step.

470 The QAF aims to develop a systematic and harmonised framework for the regulatory
471 assessment of (Q)SAR models, predictions, and results based on multiple predictions. It
472 is applicable irrespective of the modelling technique used to build the model, the predicted
473 endpoint, and the intended regulatory purpose.

474 The assessment of (Q)SARs for regulatory purposes should not be limited to checking
475 the validity of the model used because even a valid model can produce unacceptable
476 predictions under certain conditions. Therefore, individual predictions and results from
477 multiple predictions need dedicated assessments.

478 Practical implications for the implementation of SSbD

479 The findings of this study have different implications for stakeholders involved in the
480 implementation of the SSbD framework, including regulators, industry actors, and
481 researchers. In particular, they highlight both the opportunities and the current limitations
482 of relying on *in silico* tools for early-stage hazard identification.

483 For regulators, the developed workflow presented in this study demonstrates how multiple
484 *in silico* tools can be applied in a structured and transparent manner while explicitly
485 addressing uncertainty. The results highlight that different strategies for integrating model
486 outputs (e.g. majority vote, mean, or conservative approaches) can lead to different
487 assessment outcomes, even when based on the same underlying predictions. This

488 strengthens the importance of documenting not only the chosen tools but also the
489 justification of the integration strategies and decision rules in line with EFSA's WoE
490 Principles and the OECD's QAF (EFSA Scientific Committee et al., 2017; OECD, 2023a).
491 Rather than aiming for a single definitive outcome, the workflow supports regulatory use
492 of *in silico* tools as part of an iterative decision-making process, where uncertainty and
493 data gaps are explicitly stated and can be re-examined as additional information becomes
494 available.

495 For industry and innovators, particularly at early stages of chemical and material
496 development, the workflow provides a practical means to screen potential hazards before
497 significant resources are committed. The results show that *in silico* tools are well suited
498 to identifying potential areas of concern across a broad range of SSbD-relevant endpoints,
499 but also that conclusions may depend on model coverage and agreement. From a design
500 perspective, this suggests that SSbD assessments should be used to guide informed
501 choices and prioritisation rather than to deliver binary "pass/fail" decisions. Early
502 identification of potential hazard signals can support substitution, redesign, or targeted
503 data generation, while acknowledging that uncertainty is an inherent feature of early
504 innovation.

505 For researchers and tool developers, the analysis highlights several areas where further
506 methodological development is needed to support SSbD implementation. These include
507 improved harmonisation of endpoint definitions across models, clearer and more
508 consistent communication of AD information, and expanded model coverage for currently
509 underrepresented endpoints. The observed variability between models and platforms
510 also points to the need for further work on integration approaches that go beyond simple
511 aggregation, particularly for complex endpoints such as reproductive toxicity and
512 endocrine disruption. Addressing these challenges through harmonised reporting,
513 improved applicability domain diagnostics, and the development of models for currently
514 underrepresented SSbD-relevant endpoints would significantly strengthen the role of *in*
515 *silico* tools in future SSbD assessment (Benfenati et al., 2019; OECD, 2023a).

516 Overall, *in silico* tools can play a central role in operationalising SSbD, provided they are
517 applied within a transparent, well-documented framework that explicitly accounts for

518 uncertainty and context of use. Rather than replacing experimental data or expert
519 judgement, such tools are most effective when used to support early decision-making,
520 learning, and iteration throughout the innovation process.

521 Conclusions and recommendations

522 In this study, we evaluated the use of *in silico* tools to predict chemical hazards under the
523 SSbD assessment framework, however, the approach can be applied to different
524 regulatory contexts too. An SSbD assessment is an iterative process throughout the
525 innovation path, where the flow of information gradually increases moving from one
526 innovation stage to the next. In relation to the position of *in silico* tools, they are critical
527 during the earlier stages of innovation when the information is very limited and the
528 uncertainty higher. Even though these tools are commonly used for hazard predictions,
529 they present limitations regarding their incorporation into the SSbD assessment process.
530 Within the PARC SSbD toolbox, the previously discussed (Q)SAR tools, along with
531 additional *in silico* tools, have been mapped across the innovation process and the SSbD
532 framework assessments for safety and sustainability. One of the main objectives of the
533 PARC SSbD toolbox is to integrate tools and data throughout an SSbD assessment
534 pipeline. Therefore, the current study serves as a starting point for building an *in silico*
535 hazard assessment workflow in the context of the PARC SSbD toolbox development. For
536 a better-defined protocol for *in silico* hazard assessment under SSbD (and other
537 regulatory contexts), a set of recommendations is provided.

538 Prediction reliability

539 *In silico* tools are generally easy to use and don't require extensive input data. However,
540 to receive predictions that are not only rapid but also reliable, the hazard identification
541 within the SSbD framework should incorporate the evaluation of the prediction's reliability.
542 To accomplish this, a series of actions need to be implemented. First, a systematic
543 approach to integrate reliability assessment into models that do not include it within their
544 estimations should be structured. This would also facilitate the process of evaluating
545 predictions of the same endpoint by different models. Moreover, assessors should be
546 provided with comprehensive information regarding the AD status of each model,

547 including the reason why a specific structure falls outside the AD. This would allow them
548 to reach informed decisions on whether to consider a model prediction in their
549 assessment.

550 **Missing endpoints & Data gap strategy**

551 Within the iterative process of SSbD across innovation, data gaps are expected to occur,
552 particularly in the earlier stages. These data gaps need to be considered during the
553 decision-making process. In addition, from the current study, we identified hazard
554 endpoints (e.g., Specific Target Organ Toxicity – Single Exposure, physical hazards) that
555 are included in the EC SSbD framework for which predictive models are not available or
556 very limited in applicability. As a result, the interpretation of results received from SSbD
557 assessment and particularly hazard assessment, should require a comprehensive and
558 transparent approach to consider data gaps. In conjunction with the missing endpoints,
559 there is a need for future (Q)SAR model developments that cover these types of endpoints
560 and address potential data gaps within the assessment pipeline. Also, when (Q)SAR
561 models are lacking, there are other *in silico* approaches—such as read-across and expert
562 systems—that might be used to provide hazard predictions. These methods can leverage
563 chemical similarity, mechanistic reasoning, or weight-of-evidence approaches to reduce
564 uncertainty for specific endpoints or borderline cases. Future SSbD workflows could also
565 benefit from integrated strategies combining (Q)SARs with complementary *in silico*
566 methodologies to further strengthen confidence in hazard-based design decisions.

567 **Complex endpoints**

568 Another important aspect that needs to be considered is the complexity associated with
569 some of the indicators, such as reprotoxicity. The prediction and evaluation of these
570 indicators may be more challenging compared to simpler indicators. Therefore, a new
571 scheme for the assessment of a substance should be structured that integrates *in silico*
572 tools more effectively, which should be used not only to replicate a limited traditional
573 scheme. Furthermore, the integration of results from different models into a single overall
574 call should be investigated. For instance, the integration of outcomes resulting from
575 models that predict the same endpoints, such as mutations in cells, but for different
576 organisms (i.e. mouse and hamster) could be explored. Finally, an additional area of

577 investigation could entail the integration of different endpoints (i.e. different assays)
578 related to the same indicator (i.e. mutagenicity) into a single value. This would also involve
579 the strategy needed for implementation and how this could be established efficiently.

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698

699 Figure 1. Developed workflow for the assessment of hazards using in silico tools based
700 on Benfenati et al. (2019) and EFSA Scientific Committee (2017).

701 Figure 2. Share of (Q)SAR predictions, as a percentage out of all available (Q)SARs for
702 that specific property, that were considered as reliable under the 'simple' and 'advanced'
703 evaluation schemes for A) BPA, B) Isosorbide, and C) BPAP. The properties covered
704 are Persistency (P), Bioaccumulation (B), Carcinogenicity (C), Mutagenicity (M),
705 Reproductive Toxicity (R), Endocrine Disruption (ED) and Aquatic Toxicity. (Q)SAR =
706 (Quantitative) Structure-Activity Relationship; BPA = bisphenol A; BPAP = bisphenol
707 AP.

Developed workflow for the assessment of hazards using in silico tools based on Benfenati et al. (2019) and EFSA Scientific Committee (2017).

216x317mm (236 x 236 DPI)

Share of (Q)SAR predictions, as a percentage out of all available (Q)SARs for that specific property, that were considered as reliable under the 'simple' and 'advanced' evaluation schemes for A) BPA, B) Isosorbide, and C) BPAP. The properties covered are Persistence (P), Bioaccumulation (B), Carcinogenicity (C), Mutagenicity (M), Reproductive Toxicity (R), Endocrine Disruption (ED) and Aquatic Toxicity.

830x182mm (236 x 236 DPI)

Table 1. An overview of the different platforms used in this study to predict the studied hazard endpoints. A list of all the individual models used in this work is available in the SI. ¹Included and run in the QSAR Toolbox v4.6.

(Q)SAR Platform	Carcinogenicity	Mutagenicity	Reproductive toxicity	Persistence	Bioaccumulation	Endocrine Disruptions	Aquatic toxicity
VEGA 1.2.3	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
JANUS 1.0.3	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
EPI Suite v4.11	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Mistra SafeChem In-silico Toolbox	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Danish (Q)SAR database	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes ¹	Yes
QSAR Toolbox v4.6	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note. QSAR = quantitative structure-activity relationship.

Table 1. Combined results for each property for BPA, Isosorbide, and BPAP

Property	BPA	Isosorbide	BPAP
Persistency	Potential issue	Not flagged	Potential issue
Bioaccumulation	Potential issue	Not flagged	Potential issue
Carcinogenicity	Potential issue [*] , ^{**}	Not flagged [*] , ^{**}	Potential issue ^{**}
Mutagenicity	Potential issue ^{**}	Not flagged ^{**}	Potential issue ^{**}
Reprotoxicity	Potential issue ^{**}	Potential issue ^{**}	Potential issue ^{**}
Endocrine disruption	Potential issue	Not flagged	Potential issue [*]
Aquatic toxicity	Potential issue	Not flagged	Potential issue

* = inconclusive results, ** = no results for one or more models. The full list of predicted endpoints and the combined output can be found in the SI.

Note. BPA = bisphenol A; BPAP = bisphenol AP.

625x312mm (72 x 72 DPI)